

Effects of applying all or individual management components on rice yield in rainfed uplands

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Direct-seeded upland rice is an important production system for the resource-poor farmers of eastern India. With the recent emphasis on improving the productivity of this important risk-prone ecosystem, a number of technological interventions have been suggested by researchers. Application of technology components as a package is required for achieving higher productivity in upland rice. Whenever a single component of the package is not applied, productivity decreases significantly. The contribution of each technology component to increasing rainfed upland rice productivity is not investigated thoroughly. In our study, we examined the contribution of the different components of technology to rainfed upland rice productivity.

A preliminary field experiment was conducted to study the effect of individual technology components on upland rice productivity in 2000 and significant differences were observed (data not reported). Based on this information, on-farm experiments with farmers' participation were conducted in Khorahar village (Hazaribagh, India) in upland red soil during the wet seasons of 2001 and 2002. The amount of rainfall received at the site was 570.5 mm (2001) and 800.4 mm (2002), which was about 52.25% and 73.2%, respectively, of the long-term average seasonal (Jun-Oct) rainfall in the area. The year

2001 was highly unfavorable for crop growth, with the crop experiencing three dry spells of 12, 10, and 8 d, which corresponded to the tillering, reproductive, and grain-filling stage. In 2002, there was one dry spell of 9 d at the grain-filling stage.

The technology components studied were (1) fertilization (40 kg N, 13 kg P, and 16 kg K ha⁻¹); (2) weed control (two hand weeding); and (3) insect control (gamaxine at 25 kg ha⁻¹ for termites and endosulphan at 1.0 L ha⁻¹ for rice bugs). The combinations were T1 (fertilizer + weeding + insect control), T2 (weeding + insect control), T3 (fertilizer + insect control), and T4 (fertilizer + weeding). All four combinations of technology components were tested with two upland varieties, Brown Gora (traditional) and Vandana (improved), in four

farmers' fields treating farmers as replications.

Urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash were the sources of N, P, and K, respectively. Nitrogen was applied in two splits (50% 22 d after germination and 50% 40 d after germination). All P and K were applied basally at seeding. Gamaxine dust at 25 kg ha⁻¹ was mixed in the soil before seeding and endosulphan at 1.0 L ha⁻¹ was sprayed at the milking stage. At harvest, grain and straw yields were recorded and the corresponding effects of technology components were calculated.

The results of the 2-year field experiment showed that the application of all components as a package gave significantly higher yield, whereas no application of fertilizer or no weeding reduced yield significantly. There was no

Variety and treatment means for grain and straw yield (t ha⁻¹) during the 2001-02 wet seasons.

Variety and treatment	2001		2002	
	Grain yield	Straw yield	Grain yield	Straw yield
Variety				
Vandana	0.59	1.40	1.15	1.86
Brown Gora	0.82	1.36	1.08	1.93
Treatment				
T1	1.06	1.88	1.49	2.34
T2	0.33	0.62	0.75	1.34
T3	0.53	1.36	0.82	1.60
T4	0.91	1.66	1.40	2.31
LSD(0.05)				
Variety	0.13	nsa	ns	ns
Treatment	0.19	0.20	0.29	0.40
Variety × treatment	ns	ns	ns	ns

^ans = not significant.

significant difference between T1 and T4, which implies that yield reduction due to omission of insect control measures (T4) was not significant as compared with the other two components (see table). Nonapplication of fertilizer substantially reduced grain and straw yields in both cultivars. There was a significant difference in grain yield among varieties in 2001, but the variety × technology component interaction was not significant in either year. Maximum yield reduction was recorded with no fertilizer application, followed by no weeding and no insect control (see figure). Average yield data for 2 years revealed that the no-fertilization component reduced grain yield by 69% and 50% and straw yield by 67% and 43% in Vandana and Brown Gora, re-

Reduction in grain and straw yield due to nonapplication of technology components.

spectively; no weeding reduced grain yield by 50% and 45% and straw yield by 28% and 32%; and no insect control reduced grain yield by 14% and 6% and straw yield by 12% and 1%. The lower grain and straw yield reduction in local variety Brown Gora was due to its early vigor, weed competi-

tiveness, and low responsiveness to inputs. Grain yield was considerably low in 2001 as the crop suffered from moisture stress at the tillering, reproductive, and grain-filling stages. As reported by Yambao and Ingram (1988), the most severe moisture stress affecting rice yield coincides with booting to flowering /early grain filling.

Our study revealed that, among the technology components, fertilizer application and weeding control measures need special attention to achieve and sustain higher productivity in the rainfed upland rice ecosystem. Insect pest control should be implemented as needed.

Reference

Yambao EB, Ingram KT. 1988. Drought stress index for rice. Philipp. J. Crop Sci. 13:105-111.

Benefit-cost ratio in producing aromatic and nonaromatic rice genotypes in Kashmir Valley

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Kashmir is well known for the cultivation of a large number of aromatic as well as nonaromatic landraces, which occupy different agroecological niches. Most of the aromatic rice varieties are local landraces maintained by farmers since time immemorial (now preserved at various rice stations of the university). Some of these varieties possess not only good aroma but also elite morphological features, which are desirable under our valley conditions. Of the aromatic genotypes, Mushk Budgi and Kamad are in great demand and are highly priced, whereas nonaromatic rice varieties

K-332 and Jhelum (SKAU-27) are commercially grown. Since a vast difference is found in the yielding abilities of these aromatic and nonaromatic varieties, there is room for improving these aromatic cultivars. A study was carried out to determine the benefit-cost ratio (BCR) of producing these varieties to better identify the factors that may need to be manipulated to further improve these varieties.

The cost of cultivation per hectare was Rs 18,334 for Mushk Budgi, Rs 18,226 for Kamad, and Rs 16,186 for the high-yielding commercial varieties Jhelum

(under valley basins) and K-332 (under high-altitude conditions) (Table 1a). The variation in the cost of cultivation was due to the different cost of seed—Rs 18 kg⁻¹ for Mushk Budgi and Rs 15 kg⁻¹ for Kamad as against Rs 6 kg⁻¹ for Jhelum and K-332. Moreover, an additional expenditure of Rs 1,540 was incurred when prophylactic measures were taken to control blast in the local cultivars. An estimation of net income and benefits and BCR showed that the high-yielding commercial varieties gave the highest net income of Rs 28,814 and Rs 16,214 under valley basin and high-altitude con-